

$[M_1 - Me - H_2O]^+(2.3)$, 369 $[M_1 - C_8H_7]^+(3.5)$, 327 $[M_1 - 85]^+(2.3)$, 314 $[M_1 - 98]^+(4.7)$, 400 $[M_2]^+(20.9)$, 385 $[M_2 - Me]^+(7.0)$, 382 $[M_2 - H_2O]^+(20.9)$, 367 $[M_2 - Me - H_2O]^+(9.4)$, 315 $[M_2 - 85]^+(9.4)$, 289 $[M_2 - C_7H_{11}O]^+(11.7)$, 386 $[M_3]^+(4.7)$, 371 $[M_3 - Me]^+(2.3)$, 368 $[M_3 - H_2O]^+(4.7)$ and 301 $[M_3 - 85]^+(4.7)$ which can be best rationalised¹⁵⁻¹⁶ by assuming the solid to be a mixture of β -sitosterol, stigmasterol, campesterol and cholesterol or their epimers. The relative abundance of the mass peaks also suggested that sitosterol or its epimer be the major component in the mixture. This fact may also be corroborated¹⁶ by its 1H nmr spectrum in $CDCl_3$ (100 MHz, TMS as internal standard), which displayed signals at δ 0.66 (3H, s, H-18), 0.76 (3H, d, H-26 or 27 or 28 in case of campesterol), 0.82 (3H, d, H-26 or 27), 0.84 (3H, t, H-29), 0.92 (3H, d, H-21), 0.98 (3H, s, H-19), 3.52 (1H, br s, H-3), 5.01-5.12 (1H, br m, H-22 and 23) and 5.34 (1H, br s, H-6). To find out the approximate composition of the sterol mixture, the solid (0.02 g) was acetylated with acetic anhydride and pyridine and workup of the acetylated product in the usual manner afforded crystals of acetyl derivative (0.012 g), m.p. 118°. This acetyl derivative showed ir absorption (KBr) at ν_{max} 2940 (CH), 2880 (CH), 1745 (C=O), 1650 (C=C), 1510, 1410, 1295 and 1090 cm^{-1} . The EI-mass spectrum of it revealed some significant peaks at m/z (relative abundance in percent) 396 $[M_1 - HOAc]^+(100.0)$, 394 $[M_1 - HOAc]^+(15.3)$, 382 $[M_1 - HOAc]^+(20.9)$, 368 $[M_1 - HOAc]^+(2.3)$, 287 (16.3), 275 (14.0) 255 (54.7), 228 (7.0), 213 (48.7), 147 (61.6), 145 (48.8), 107 (32.6), 105 (34.9), 81 (66.3), 55 (55.8) and 43 (69.7) which may be explained by considering the acetyl derivative as an acetate mixture of sitosterol, stigmasterol, campesterol and cholesterol. The 1H nmr spectrum (100 MHz) of this acetyl derivative in $CDCl_3$ (TMS as internal standard) displayed signals at δ 0.67 (3H, s, H-18), 0.78 (3H, d, H-26 or 27 or 28), 0.85 (3H, d, H-26 or 27), 0.87 (3H, t, H-29), 0.94 (3H, d, H-21), 1.01 (3H, s, H-19), 2.01 (3H, s, acetate), 3.60 (1H, m, H-3), 5.01-5.16 (1H, br m, H-22 and 23) and 5.38 (1H, br s, H-6) which are diagnostic of Δ^5 sterols. This acetyl derivative was gas chromatographed on a Pye-Unicam 104 instrument using a glass column packed with 3% OV-17 on 100-120 mesh Gas Chrom Q. The chromatographic conditions were: column temperature, 250°; FID and injection port temperature 280°; carrier gas (N_2) at the flow rate 50 ml/min and chart speed 320 mm/h. The acetyl derivative was found to contain four phytosterols which were identified by comparison RR ,¹⁶⁻¹⁸ with respect to cholesteryl acetate. It was identified as the mixture of the acetates of cholesterol [cholest-5-en-3 β -ol] (R , 1.00, 3.0% by peak area); campesterol [(24*R*)-24-methyl-cholest-5-en-3 β -ol] [1.32, 12.5%], stigmasterol [(24*S*)-24-ethylcholesta-5, *E*-22-dien-3 β -ol] (1.46, 15.5%) and β -sitosterol [(24*R*)-24-ethylcholest-5-en-3 β -ol] (1.64; 69.0%). This relative abundance value may change as the epimers of the said sterols have also same RR , values.

The sterols are the metabolites of many secondary metabolism, so the occurrence of these sterols may lead us to find out some compounds which are still eluded to be isolated from the plant.

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Phytochemical Study of *Indigofera mysorensis* Rottl. (N.O. Leguminosae) Leaves

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THE members belonging to the genus *Indigofera* (fam.: *Leguminosae*; sub-fam.: *Papilionoidae*) are widely used in indigenous medicine as anthelmintics, febrifuges and in the treatment of skin

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diseases¹. Nearly thirty members of the genus are available in India, almost all of them are chemically investigated². We report herein a few polyphenolic constituents from *I. mysorensis* Rottl, which is the first report from this species.

The dried leaves of *I. mysorensis* (0.5 kg) (material collected near Tirupati, District Chittoor) were successively extracted with solvents of increasing polarity. The dry acetone extract (15 g) was macerated with dry ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate soluble fraction on chromatographic separation and purification (silica gel G column, benzene-ethyl acetate, 8:2, 6:4, 1:1, 2:8) afforded two crystalline compounds A and B which were found to be phenolic acids, on the basis the uv and ir data. They were identified as (A) protocatechuic acid and (B) *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid by comparison of m.p. and m.m.p. with the authentic samples.

The ethyl acetate insoluble fraction on separation by pc (two-dimensional, Whatman 3 mm, butanol-acetone-water (v/v) 4:1:5, 15% AcOH) and purification yielded two yellow compounds C and D, which by colour reactions and *R_f* data were found to be flavonoid-*O*-glycosides. The uv data of the compounds in methanol and shifts with diagnostic reagents indicated that the sugar units were present in 7- and 3-positions in compounds C and D, respectively.

The products of acid hydrolysis using 7% H₂SO₄ and the difficulty in hydrolysis of compound C showed clearly that the sugar unit was present in 7-position and it was rhamnoglucose. The aglycone was identified as apigenin. Complete methylation of compound C with dimethyl sulphate and K₂CO₃ and subsequent hydrolysis gave an aglycone identified as 5,4'-dimethylapigenin³. Compound C was thus identified as apigenin-7-rhamnoglucoside rhoifolin, which was confirmed by the nmr data of the glycoside.

Compound D underwent easy hydrolysis with 5% H₂SO₄, giving rise to kaempferol and the sugars, rhamnose and glucose. The nmr data of the compound showed that the sugar unit was neohesperidoside⁴. Thus compound D was identified as kaempferol-3-neohesperidoside.

The dried methanol extract on chromatographic separation over a polyamide column and further purification with aqueous methanol (1:1) eluent yielded an orange-red compound E. The chromatographic and uv data indicated that the compound was a flavone-*O*-glycoside, and was identified as apigenin-7,4'-diglucoside depending on the products of acid hydrolysis (apigenin and glucose) and comparison of the *R_f* data in different solvent systems⁵.

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Complexation of Silver(I) with Morpholinylthiocarbonyl Acid Amide and its Use as an Amperometric Reagent for Trace Determination of Silver(I)

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THE present work reports an analytical and ir spectral examination of Ag^I complex with morpholinylthiocarbonyl acid amide (MTA). Based on the complexation of Ag^I with MTA, an amperometric method for the determination of traces of silver has also been developed.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade. The ligand, (4-morpholinyl)thiocarbonyl acid amide (MTA) was prepared by the reported method¹. The crude product was purified by recrystallisation from ethanol (Found: C, 41.2; H, 6.81; N, 19.19; S, 21.85. C₅H₁₀N₂O₃ calcd. for: C, 41.09; H, 6.84; N, 19.17; S, 21.91%).

Ag^I MTA complex: To a cold aqueous solution of ligand (1 mmol) an aqueous solution of silver nitrate (1 mmol) was added with constant stirring, and the resulting white precipitate was allowed to settle, filtered and washed thoroughly with distilled water and finally dried in vacuum (Found: Ag, 53.15; C, 19.00; H, 3.20; N, 8.73; S, 10.18. Calcd. for: Ag, 53.17; C, 18.99; H, 3.16; N, 8.86; S, 10.13%).

The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 grating infrared spectrophotometer in the range 4 000-650 cm⁻¹.

Results and Discussion

Ir bands due to ν_{NH} (3 410-3 200 cm⁻¹) in ligand show decrease in intensity and broadening

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